

EFFECTIVENESS OF MODULAR APPROACH TO TEACHING AND LEARNERS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

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Effectiveness of Modular Approach to Teaching and Learners' Academic Achievement in Araling Panlipunan

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Abstract

This study was crafted and launched to find the relationship between the effectiveness of modular approach to teaching and learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan at Sumilao District, SY 2020-2021. The descriptive correlational research design was used. It was conducted in the elementary schools of Sumilao District, Division of Bukidnon, school year 2020-2021. This study requested the teachers of the small, medium, and big schools of Sumilao District, Division of Bukidnon to be the respondents. The researcher adopted the instrument of Vergara (2017). The researcher made a slight modification to fit the instrument to the present study. The following statistical tools were used in this study: percentage and frequency, mean and standard deviation, percentage and frequency count, and Pearson r Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson. This study found out that most of the parents/learners had positive responses to the modules. Few had negative responses and neutral responses. The modular approach to teaching in terms of content, language, presentation, assessment were perceived by the teachers as highly effective in all its indicators. Majority of the learners had very satisfactory academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. The variables contents, language, presentation and assessment had a positive significant relationship with the learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. There was a significant relationship between the responses of parents/learners to the modules and the learners' academic achievement. This study offers the following recommendations: the teachers and school heads may entertain the parents and learners positively whenever they come to school to get or to return modules. The teachers may continue to follow the MELC or Most Essential Learning Competency in printing the modules and providing the activity sheets. The parents may continue to guide their children so that their high grades or very satisfactory grades can be sustained. The Department of Education may continue to produce modules that have contents, language, presentation, and assessment which are significantly related for the attainment of good grades of the learners. The parents/learners may maintain their positive responses that they have for the modules as it has a significant relationship to the academic achievement of the learners.

Keywords: *effectiveness, modular approach, teaching, learners, academic achievement, Araling Panlipunan*

Introduction

The images utilized by critics and pessimists as evidence of the impracticality of distance learning—depicting teachers, learners, and parents struggling to maintain "classes" off-campus under difficult circumstances—serve as compelling justification for why Filipino children should not forfeit this academic year by default (Ciriaco, 2020).

Reopening schools during the COVID-19 pandemic presents significant challenges that the Department of Education (DepEd) has encountered as nations worldwide, including the Philippines, strive to maintain educational continuity amid the health crisis. Days prior to the commencement of the 2020–2021 academic year, on October 5, Education Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones articulated her pride in the Department of Education's advancements within a span of less than six months, asserting that "one can overhaul virtually the entire educational system, modify the curriculum, and alter the methods of education and learning delivery in a matter of months." She takes pride in the collective efforts of all stakeholders—teachers, parents, learners, and school officials—in achieving what once seemed unattainable: enabling millions of learners to continue their education outside traditional classrooms, from various residences, and even from makeshift locations such as an abandoned jeepney, a discarded shed, beneath a tree, or atop a hill where the Internet signal is robust.

Briones acknowledged the criticisms and skepticism directed at the Department of Education, with some factions advocating for the abandonment of blended learning due to its complexities and suggesting an academic freeze instead. She highlighted that the school system's and stakeholders' ability to respond positively reflects the capacity of the department and Philippine society, including parents and teachers, to foresee potential challenges and develop appropriate solutions. To maintain physical distancing, Parañaque Elementary School Central has provided boxes outside the school where parents can drop off their children's enrollment and survey forms. The survey includes questions about the learner's access to resources for remote education, such as electronic devices and Internet connectivity. DepEd has directed its field offices and teachers to determine the most suitable off-campus learning methods for learners based on their community setting. Most parents have chosen modular learning for their children over other options. Initial results from the Learner Enrollment and Survey Form (LESF) indicate that 8.8 million parents preferred modular learning, while 3.9 million opted for blended learning, which combines modalities like modules, television, radio, or online resources.

Only 3.8 million parents choose to utilize internet resources. Approximately 1.4 million parents preferred instructional television, while at least 900,000 opted for radio-based instruction. Approximately 500,000 parents selected alternate solutions.

Sevilla pledged to maintain a 1:1 ratio by not disseminating any self-learning modules (SLMs) for the 2020-2021 academic year. In 2020, we created ways to ensure a 1:1 ratio. Sevilla stated, "We realigned and re-prioritized," highlighting that they had utilized the Special Education Fund to address the increasing demands of off-school learning following the support from local government units (LGUs).

In a previous interview, Diosdado San Antonio, the Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction, stated that he will provide the remaining 20% of the modules before the start of classes. San Antonio has made sure to disinfect the modules before dispatch. Revsee Escobeo, the Undersecretary of Field Operations, anticipates the completion of 667,673,924 printed SLMs by the first quarter of 2021. The Department of Education indicated that self-learning modules (SLMs) have been its primary emphasis, as modular learning is the preferred educational approach in various regions.

This study aimed to explore the relationship between the effectiveness of a modular teaching strategy and learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan in the Sumilao District for the 2020-2021 school year.

Research Questions

This study was shaped and launched to find the relationship between the effectiveness of modular approach to teaching and learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan at Sumilao District, SY 2020-2021. In particular, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the responses of the parents/learners to the modules as observed by the teachers?
2. What is the level of effectiveness of a modular approach to teaching in terms of: Contents, Language, Presentation, and Assessment?
3. What is the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of modular approach to teaching and learner's academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the responses of the parents/learners to the modules and the learner's academic achievement?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the effectiveness of the modular teaching approach and its relationship with learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan within the Sumilao District, Division of Bukidnon. Data on the modular approach's effectiveness were collected through a researcher-designed questionnaire, while learners' academic achievement was measured by their average grades in Araling Panlipunan for the second quarter of the 2020-2021 school year.

Respondents

This study invited teachers from small, medium, and large schools within the Sumilao District, Division of Bukidnon, to serve as respondents.

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents by school.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by School*

<i>School</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>
Kisolon CES	72
Sumilao ES	38
Vista Villa ES	9
Total	119

This study employed purposive sampling as the sampling method, specifically targeting public school teachers from the selected schools in the Sumilao District. Through this approach, all public-school teachers from the identified schools were included as respondents to ensure a comprehensive understanding of perspectives on the effectiveness of the modular approach in teaching. This sampling method allowed the study to capture insights directly from those implementing the instructional approach, providing valuable data on both its implementation and outcomes for learners' academic achievement.

Instrument

The study utilized an adapted version of Vergara's (2017) instrument, modified slightly by the researcher to better align with the current study's context. The survey-questionnaire comprised three parts. Part I focused on responses from parents and learners to the modules, as observed by the teachers, with each area containing five items. Responses were recorded using a five-point Likert scale, with respondents marking their answer in the appropriate column.

Part II assessed the perceived effectiveness of the modular teaching approach across four dimensions: Content, Language, Presentation, and Assessment.

Part III gathered information on learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. Specifically, it requested the learners' average grade in Araling Panlipunan for the second quarter of the 2019-2020 school year, as provided by the teachers handling the subject.

Procedure

This research adhered to a structured protocol to maintain high standards in conducting the study at VCI. Initially, a permission and endorsement letter was secured from the Dean of Graduate Studies, which was subsequently sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bukidnon. Upon receiving approval, the researcher sought permission from the Public Schools District Supervisors of the Sumilao District. Following this, approval was also requested from the School Heads of the selected schools to facilitate the study within their institutions. Finally, questionnaires were distributed to the identified respondents.

Data Analysis

This study utilized the following statistical tools: percentage and frequency counts were used to evaluate the implementation status of the modular approach in schools, focusing on the proportion of modules claimed and returned on time, as well as teachers' observations of parents' and learners' responses to the modules.

To determine the effectiveness of the modular teaching approach, the mean and standard deviation were calculated and analyzed, again considering module claim and return rates and observed responses from parents and learners.

Percentage and frequency counts were also applied to assess and categorize the academic achievement levels of elementary learners in Araling Panlipunan.

A t-test was conducted to determine any significant differences in the implementation status of the modular approach across schools, including module claim and return rates and observed responses from parents and learners, as well as in the effectiveness of the modular teaching approach.

Finally, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was employed to investigate the significant relationship between the effectiveness of the modular teaching approach and learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data collected from the respondents. The presentation follows the sequence outlined in the study's statement of the problem.

It includes responses from parents and learners regarding the modules, as observed by teachers, and evaluates the effectiveness of the modular teaching approach in terms of content, language, presentation, and assessment, as well as the academic performance of learners in Araling Panlipunan. Additionally, this chapter examines the significant relationship between the effectiveness of the modular teaching approach and learners' academic performance, as well as the relationship between the responses of parents and learners to the modules and learners' academic achievement.

Table 2 is the result taken from the responses of the parents/learners to the modules as observed by the teachers. Their responses were categorized as positive, negative, neutral and others. The frequency and percentage are included in the table.

Table 2. *Responses of the Parents/Learners to the Modules as Observed by the Teachers*

<i>Responses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Positive	95	79.8
Negative	3	2.5
Neutral	21	17.6
Total	119	100

As shown in Table 2, most of the parents/learners had positive responses to the modules (freq = 95 or 79.8%). Few had negative responses (freq = 3 or 2.5%) and Neutral responses (freq = 21 or 17.6%). No parent/learner had other responses other than those specified. This suggests that many parents and learners hold positive views toward the use of modules, a strategy that was implemented even before COVID-19. Modular teaching is a widely acknowledged educational approach used in various countries, including several Western and Asian nations. It is applied across multiple fields, such as the natural sciences—particularly biology and medical education—as well as the social sciences and computer education, as noted by Manlove and David (cited in Sadiq and Zamir, 2014). This approach considers individual differences among learners, requiring the planning and use of effective teaching strategies to support each learner's personal growth and development at their own pace.

Tables 3, 4, 5, and 6 are the level of effectiveness of modular approach to teaching in terms of: Contents, Language, Presentation, and Assessment, respectively. The corresponding mean, standard deviation and qualitative description are presented in the table.

Table 3. *Level of Effectiveness of Modular Approach to Teaching in terms of Contents*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. The contents match the learning competencies following the K-12 Curriculum.	4.09	.759	Highly Effective
2. Topics are relevant to the daily activities of the learner	3.97	.730	Highly Effective
3. The contents are sensitive to the culture of the learner	3.96	.796	Highly Effective
4. Examples are easy to understand for learners.	3.86	.773	Highly Effective
5. The topics are clear and easy to understand	3.84	.638	Highly Effective
Overall	3.94	.642	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.21–5.00 (Very Highly Effective) | 3.41–4.20 (Highly Effective) | 2.61–3.40 (Moderately Effective) | 1.81–2.60 (Least Effective) | 1.00–1.80 (Not Effective)

Table 3 shows that the modular approach to teaching, in terms of content, was deemed highly effective by teachers across all indicators. The highest mean score (mean = 4.09, sd = .759) was for the statement that the content aligns with the learning competencies outlined in the K-12 Curriculum. This suggests that the modules created by teachers for reproduction and distribution were well-aligned with the MELC (Most Essential Learning Competencies). The modules were carefully crafted by the authors and thoroughly reviewed by evaluators to ensure adherence to the K-12 Curriculum. The development of modules helps guide the planning and creation of modular materials, with module writers establishing a unified framework for their design and development. According to Brown and Atkins, cited in Sadiq and Zamir (2014), teachers must understand the concepts of deep and surface learning approaches when creating modules. Numerous studies have explored the relationship between course content and the learning approaches adopted by learners. For instance, Martn, Saljo, et al., cited in Sadiq and Zamir (2014), identified a positive correlation between curriculum and learning styles.

The statement "The topics are clear and easy to understand" received the lowest mean (mean = 3.84, sd = .638). This was due to some complaints from parents and learners, who found the modules difficult to answer and hard to understand.

Overall, the modular approach to teaching content was seen as highly effective by teachers (mean = 3.94, sd = .642). This suggests that, overall, the modules are considered highly successful in terms of content for implementing a modular approach. The module design process involves three key steps: planning, drafting, and revising the module after its initial implementation. This process includes identifying the needs of the target audience and selecting an appropriate topic. Pareek et al., cited in Sadiq and Zamir (2014), outlined five key elements in module design: situation, learned capability, object, action, and tools or other limitations. Relevant information about the subject is gathered to confirm the need for a new program or module, followed by formulating plans for module development and establishing module objectives based on the needs assessment results.

Table 4. *Level of Effectiveness of Modular Approach to Teaching in terms of Language*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. The language promotes culture sensitivity and good values.	3.92	.810	Highly Effective
2. Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English sentences are easy to understand	3.85	.766	Highly Effective
3. The words use matches to the language of learners and adults	3.82	.736	Highly Effective
4. The use of words are arranged to prevent misinterpretation	3.77	.682	Highly Effective
5. The jargon and terminology use are familiar to the learners	3.73	.778	Highly Effective
Overall	3.82	.648	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.21–5.00 (Very Highly Effective) | 3.41–4.20 (Highly Effective) | 2.61–3.40 (Moderately Effective) | 1.81–2.60 (Least Effective) | 1.00–1.80 (Not Effective)

The teachers rated all indicators of the modular approach to teaching in terms of language in Table 4 as highly effective. The statement "The language promotes cultural sensitivity and good values" received the highest mean (mean = 3.92, sd = .810). This indicates that the language used in developing the modules was carefully crafted to encourage positive values in learners while being culturally sensitive.

The statement "The jargon and terminology used are familiar to the learners" received the lowest mean (mean = 3.73, sd = .778). This was because there was minimal use of jargon or specialized terminology in the modules' content.

Overall, teachers perceived the modular approach to teaching in terms of language as highly effective (mean = 3.82, sd = .648). This suggests that the language used in the development of the modules was clear, easy to understand, and beneficial for learners, with commendable qualities.

Table 5. *Level of Effectiveness of Modular Approach to Teaching in terms of Presentation*

Indicator	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1. The font size are readable specially to adult learner	3.98	.792	Highly Effective
2. The pictures and drawing used matches the topics in the module	3.83	.806	Highly Effective
3. The contents are presented in logical manner	3.82	.709	Highly Effective
4. Pictures and drawings are both familiar to the learner	3.81	.846	Highly Effective
5. Pictures and Drawing are easy to view specially to adult learner	3.64	.963	Highly Effective
Overall	3.82	.686	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.21–5.00 (Very Highly Effective) | 3.41–4.20 (Highly Effective) | 2.61–3.40 (Moderately Effective) | 1.81–2.60 (Least Effective) | 1.00–1.80 (Not Effective)

Table 5 shows that all indicators of the modular approach to teaching in terms of presentation were highly effective. The statement "The font size is readable, especially for adult learners" received the highest mean (mean = 3.98, sd = .792), indicating that the font

size of the module text was large enough for all age groups, meeting standard readability requirements.

The statement "The pictures and drawings are simple and easy to view, especially for adult learners" received the lowest mean (mean = 3.64, sd = .963). This was due to the fact that not all modules included pictures or drawings, with some consisting of plain text only.

Overall, teachers viewed the modular approach to teaching in terms of presentation as highly effective (mean = 3.82, sd = .686), meaning the modules were highly successful in terms of their physical presentation.

Table 6. *Level of Effectiveness of Modular Approach to Teaching in terms of Assessment*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	The number of question is adequate from the topic	4.00	.725	Highly Effective
2.	Evaluation matched the content of the topic	3.98	.701	Highly Effective
3.	The assessment develop higher order thinking skills	3.97	.688	Highly Effective
4.	Key answer for the assessment are clear and easy to understand	3.94	.705	Highly Effective
5.	Questions are easy to understand	3.80	.787	Highly Effective
	Overall	3.94	.632	Highly Effective

Scale: 4.21–5.00 (Very Highly Effective) | 3.41–4.20 (Highly Effective) | 2.61–3.40 (Moderately Effective) | 1.81–2.60 (Least Effective) | 1.00–1.80 (Not Effective)

As shown in Table 6, the teachers perceived the modular approach to teaching in terms of assessment as highly effective. The statement "The number of questions is appropriate for the topic" received the highest mean (mean = 4.00, sd = .725), indicating that the modules contained a sufficient number of test items related to the subject matter. This suggests that the assessments were neither too easy nor too difficult, and they were appropriately structured for a remote learning environment. Key characteristics of a module include being self-contained, an independent instructional unit, well-planned, well-defined, and equipped with a mechanism for evaluating learner work (Kandarp Sejpal, 2013; Brown et al., as cited by Sadiq and Zamir, 2014).

Other highly effective indicators included "The evaluation matches the content of the topic" (mean = 3.98, sd = .701), "The assessment encourages higher-order thinking skills" (mean = 3.97, sd = .688), "The answers for the assessment are clear and easy to understand" (mean = 3.94, sd = .705), and "The questions are easy to understand" (mean = 3.80, sd = .787). These findings indicate that the modules were carefully designed, with questions aligning with the content, promoting higher-order thinking, providing clear and understandable answers, and being easy for learners to grasp and respond to.

Research by Sadiq and Zamir (2014) on the effectiveness of the modular approach in university-level instruction found that modular teaching is more effective than other methods. This approach allows learners to progress at their own pace, supports self-directed learning, and provides quick reinforcement and feedback, which enhances learner motivation and engagement.

Table 7 is the academic achievement of the learners in Araling Panlipunan. The frequency, percent and qualitative Interpretation of the interval of grades are shown in the table.

Table 7. *Academic Achievement of the Learners in Araling Panlipunan*

<i>Grades</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Qualitative Interpretation</i>
90 and Above	17	14.3	Outstanding
85 - 89	56	47.1	Very Satisfactory
80 - 84	42	35.3	Satisfactory
75 - 79	4	3.4	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and Below	0	0	Did not Meet Expectations

As shown in Table 7, the majority of learners achieved very satisfactory academic results in Araling Panlipunan, with grades ranging from 85 to 89 (frequency = 56 or 47.1%). This suggests that learners were able to achieve high grades despite the absence of formal classroom instruction. Ali (2010) studied the effectiveness of modular teaching in biology at the secondary level in Asian Social Science, focusing on its impact on learner performance. The findings of the study supported the modular teaching approach, highlighting a notable gender difference in overall comprehension, with male learners outperforming females in comprehension-based assessments. Ali recommended the widespread implementation of this approach in traditional classrooms across various educational levels. He also concluded that most learning packages are designed for individual use, although group experiences can be incorporated.

The next largest group of learners had satisfactory academic achievement, with grades between 80 and 84% (frequency = 42 or 35.3%), indicating that some learners received fair grades. There were also a few learners who excelled, achieving grades of 90 and above (frequency = 17 or 14.3%). This demonstrates that a small number of learners earned very high scores. Only a very few learners achieved grades between 75 and 79 (frequency = 4 or 3.4%), suggesting that only a minimal number of learners received a satisfactory or passing grade.

The primary reason for incorporating modules into the teaching and learning process is their ability to address significant educational challenges. This is due to their adherence to essential criteria for promoting successful learning and their remarkable flexibility in implementation. These learning packages are designed to cater to individual needs, allowing learners to progress at their own pace.

Table 8 is the test of significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of modular approach to teaching and learner's academic

achievement in Araling Panlipunan using the Kendall's Tau sub-b correlations. The variables, correlation coefficients and p-values are presented in the table.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Effectiveness of Modular Approach to Teaching and Learner's Academic Achievement in Araling Panlipunan*

Variable	Kendall's b	p-value	Interpretation
Contents	.206	.006	Significant
Language	.294	.000	Significant
Presentation	.433	.000	Significant
Assessment	.205	.008	Significant

As shown in Table 8, the variables of Content ($b = .206$, $p\text{-value} = .006$), Language ($b = .294$, $p\text{-value} = .000$), Presentation ($b = .433$, $p\text{-value} = .000$), and Assessment ($b = .205$, $p\text{-value} = .008$) all have a positive and significant relationship with learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan. Among these, the variable "Presentation" showed a moderate relationship, while the other variables had weak relationships with the subject. These findings highlight the significance of content, language, presentation, and assessment in contributing to the academic success of learners, even amid the significant increase in COVID-19 cases.

Malik (2012) examined the impact of modular versus traditional teaching methods on learners' overall comprehension, specifically at the secondary school level. The study was conducted in both a male and a female secondary school, with a random sample of ninth-grade learners selected for the experiment. Data were collected using a teacher-created general comprehension assessment, and statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) with an independent samples t-test.

The results revealed significant differences in overall comprehension between the modular and traditional teaching methods. Learners taught using the modular method scored higher on the general comprehension test compared to those taught through traditional methods. The study also found a gender disparity, with male learners outperforming female learners in terms of general comprehension.

As a result, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant relationship between the effectiveness of the modular teaching method and learners' academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan, is rejected.

Vergara's (2017) research on the development, effectiveness, and acceptability of a module designed to enhance problem-solving and critical thinking skills in the Alternative Learning System in the Tanay II district concluded that the module was highly acceptable in terms of content, language, presentation, and assessment. Married teachers rated the module for problem-solving and critical thinking as more acceptable than their single counterparts. Learner performance improved significantly after exposure to the module. Additionally, no significant differences in learner performance were found based on sex, monthly family income, ethnicity, or reasons for dropping out. However, married, older individuals who were employed and had a high school diploma performed better.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Relationship between the Responses of the Parents/Learners to the Modules and the Learner's Academic Achievement*

Variable	Kendall's b	p-value	Interpretation
Parents'/learners' Responses to the Modules	-.368	.000	Significant

Table 9 shows that there is a significant relationship between the responses of parents/learners to the modules and the learners' academic achievement ($\tau b = -.368$, $p\text{-value} = .000$). The responses of parents and learners showed a strong correlation with the children's academic performance. Their positive adaptation to and acceptance of the modular approach significantly contributed to improvements in learners' grades. The modular approach increases the potential for learner engagement in class, especially in terms of timely completion of assigned activities. It allows learners to study at their own pace and according to their personal learning preferences. Additionally, this method has proven to be highly effective for instructing university learners pursuing a master's in educational planning and management. The modular approach could be widely applied across various disciplines and educational levels, as it effectively meets diverse learning needs at every stage.

This pedagogical approach is unique, requiring that teachers receive proper training in designing and implementing modules for classroom use. As a result, the null hypothesis, which asserts that there is no significant relationship between parents' and learners' responses to the modules and learners' academic progress, is rejected.

Research by Kochhar S.K. (2008), Singh Y.K., Sharma T.K., Upadhyay Brijesh (2008), Riasat Ali (2010), and Knight (2002) suggests that modules are not created in isolation but are integrated into the broader framework of a course or program. Additionally, studies by Marton and Saljo, as cited by Sadiq and Zamir (2014), further support the advantages of thoughtful module design.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the study: Many parents and learners have positive attitudes toward the use of modules, as this approach was already in place before the COVID-19 pandemic.

The modules prepared by the teachers for reproduction and distribution were well-aligned with the learning competencies of the MELC

(Most Essential Learning Competencies). The language used in the modules was carefully crafted to not only facilitate learning but also to promote good values and be culturally sensitive. The text size in the modules was large enough for learners of all ages to read comfortably, following a standard format that should be consistently adhered to. Additionally, the modules contained a sufficient number of test items relevant to each topic.

Despite the lack of in-person classroom instruction, learners achieved high grades. The effectiveness of the content, language, presentation, and assessment contributed significantly to the academic success of the learners, even during the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Furthermore, the responses from parents and learners were significantly linked to the academic performance of the learners. Their positive reception and acceptance of the modular approach played a key role in the high academic achievements of the learners.

This study offers the following recommendations: Teachers and school heads may maintain the positive attitudes of parents and learners towards the modules. They may greet them warmly whenever they come to school to pick up or return modules.

Teachers may continue to follow the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) in preparing and printing the modules and activity sheets.

Parents may keep assisting their children to ensure that their high or very satisfactory grades are sustained.

The Department of Education may produce modules with content, language, presentation, and assessment that are significantly linked to the attainment of good grades for learners.

Parents and learners may preserve their positive attitudes toward the modules, as these responses are significantly related to the academic achievement of the learners.

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